

NOTES

acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer medium at room temperature. This paper reports a detailed study of the titanium-pyrogallol-PH system and a method has been proposed for the determination of titanium in minerals and alloys.

Experimental

A Beckmann DB spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements. The pH measurements were carried out using an Elico digital pH meter with glasscalomel electrode assembly. All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade unless otherwise mentioned.

Potassium titanyl oxalate (0.4 g) was heated with ammonium sulphate (1 g) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (10 ml) for 10 min, then cooled to room temperature and made upto 100 ml with water. The titanium content was determined gravimetrically with cupferron². A working solution ($10 \mu g \text{ ml}^{-1}$) was prepared by diluting the standard solution with water.

The purity of PH (Bayer) was checked volumetrically using ceric sulphate³ and a 0.5% solution was prepared in chloroform. A 10% aqueous solution of pyrogallol was prepared fresh. Buffer solutions in the pH range 0.65–5.2 were prepared with 1M sodium acetate and 1M HCl.

Procedure : To an aliquot containing upto 70 μg of titanium(IV) were added buffer solution (1 ml), 10% pyrogallol (2 ml) and 0.5% PH in chloroform (3 ml). The mixture was equilibrated for 2 min and the organic phase was transferred. The aqueous phase was once again equilibrated with the reagent (2 ml). The two organic phases were mixed, dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and made upto 10 ml with chloroform. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 395 nm against a reagent blank.

Application in mineral samples : A known weight of the mineral sample was digested with HNO_3 following the standard method and the residue was dissolved in 3% HNO_3 . An aliquot of this solution containing around 50 μg of titanium(IV) was evaporated to dryness to remove nitric acid. The residue was heated with ammonium sulphate (0.2 g) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (1 ml) and the paste formed was dissolved in water (5 ml). The iron(III) in the solution was masked with 10% ascorbic acid (2 ml) and the amount of titanium was determined by following the procedure described above.

Application in alloys : A known quantity of the alloy sample was dissolved in H_2SO_4 in the presence of ammonium sulphate. An aliquot of the solution containing around 50 μg of titanium was taken, iron(III) was masked with 20% ascorbic acid (2 ml) and the amount of titanium was determined following the above procedure.

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Titanium in Minerals and Alloys

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DURING a systematic study on *N*-alkylphenothiazine¹ it has been found that promethazine hydrochloride (PH) forms a mixed-ligand complex with titanium(IV) in the presence of pyrogallol in sodium

Results and Discussion

Titanium(IV) reacts with pyrogallol in the presence of promethazine hydrochloride at room temperature in sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer (pH 1.5–5.2) to form an yellowish orange mixed ligand complex which can be extracted into an organic solvent.

Among the various solvents, such as chloroform, chlorobenzene, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, toluene, xylene, diethyl ether, butyl acetate and ethyl acetate, it was found that chloroform was most suitable as the extractant exhibited high sensitivity, selectivity and stability.

In a 10 ml of final solution containing 70 μg of titanium(IV), 1–4 ml of 10% pyrogallol and 3–7 ml of 0.5% PH solutions were necessary for maximum colour development. Hence 2 ml of 10% pyrogallol and 5 ml of 0.5% PH solution were chosen for all subsequent work. The colour development was almost instantaneous and the absorbance remained constant for 72 h. Absorption spectra of the mixed-ligand complex exhibited maximum absorbance at 395 nm at which the reagent blank exhibited negligible absorbance.

Beer's law was obeyed over the range 0.4–7.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of titanium(IV). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were $6.71 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0071 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2} \text{ Ti}^{\text{IV}}$ respectively. For 10 parallel determinations of $5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Ti^{IV} , the relative error and standard deviation were ± 0.0032 and $\pm 0.92\%$ respectively. The probable composition of the extracted species as determined by the Job's method of continuous variation⁴ and equilibrium shift method⁵ was found to be 1 : 3 : 1 (titanium : pyrogallol : PH).

The extent of interference by cations and anions usually associated with titanium in minerals and alloys were determined by measuring the absorbance of a solution containing $5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of titanium and various diverse ions. An error of $\pm 2\%$ was considered tolerable. The tolerance limits of diverse ions in the determination of $5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1} \text{ Ti}^{\text{IV}}$ are as follows (figures in the parenthesis represent tolerance limit in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$): Na^{I} , K^{I} , Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} (8000), Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} (2000), Al^{III} (1000), Ni^{II} and La^{III} (400), Cr^{III} (150), Sn^{II} and Ce^{IV} (100), Cu^{II} and Th^{IV} (80), U^{VI} (60), Pb^{II} (50), Co^{II} and V^{V} (40), W^{VI} (10), EDTA (5000), chloride, sulphate, acetate, oxalate and tartarate (1100), nitrate, phosphate and bromide (400), iodide (200) and fluoride (20). For Fe^{III} the tolerance limit was $250 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in the presence of 2 ml of 20% ascorbic acid as masking agent.

In order to confirm the usefulness of the proposed method it was applied in the determination of titanium in some mineral samples and iron-titanium-aluminium alloy. The results are presented in Table 1 which shows that the values are comparable with the certified values.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF TITANIUM IN MINERALS AND ALLOYS

Sample	Certified value* TiO_2 %	Found** TiO_2 %
Mineral ^a		
MRG-1	3.690	3.660
ASK-1	1.168	1.160
ASK-2	0.918	0.910
SY-3	0.150	0.148
Fe-Ti-Al alloy ^b	8.0 ^c	8.09 ^c

* *Geostandard Newsletter*, 1984, 832. ** Average of five determinations.

^aAtomic Minerals Division, Bangalore.

^bVISL Bhadravathi. ^cPercentage of Ti.

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